

What is the Intelligence Level Can Increase Employee Performance PT. PLN?

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ABSTRACT: In the business world, companies need high performance. Performance is the result or overall success rate of a person over a period of time in carrying out tasks compared to various possibilities, such as predetermined standards of work, targets, or criteria. The purpose of the study was to analyze the influence of intellectual intelligence, emotional intelligence, and spiritual intelligence on employee performance. The population in this study were 63 employees of PT PLN (Persero). This study uses quantitative associative, with data analysis used is multiple linear regression analysis. The results showed that both intellectual intelligence, emotional intelligence, and spiritual intelligence had a positive and significant effect on employee performance. Intellectual intelligence has the greatest influence on employee performance, followed by spiritual intelligence and emotional intelligence. Intellectual intelligence, emotional intelligence and spiritual intelligence together have an effect of 52.4% on employee performance, and the remaining 47.6% is influenced by other factors not explained in this study.

Keywords: Employee Performance, Intellectual Intelligence, Emotional Intelligence, Spiritual Intelligence

I. INTRODUCTION

Human resources (HR) is one of the key factors in economic reform, namely how to create qualified and skilled human resources and highly competitive in global competition (Herminingsih, 2017). The position of HR, especially about the quality of human resources in a larger system, namely organizational strategy. HR Employees or management are increasingly recognized as strategic assets of an organization (Nurhayati, 2018).

The level of success of a company in managing the resources it has to be able to improve work efficiency and effectiveness. The company's success and performance can be seen from the performance achieved by its employees, therefore the company demands that its employees be able to display optimal performance because the poor performance achieved by employees will affect the performance and success of the company as a whole (Sulastris et al., 2016).

PT PLN (Persero) Sumatra Java Interconnection Development Unit Java is a company in the electricity sector that is trusted in the construction of High Voltage Direct Current (HVDC) technology, which is the main transmission cable placed under the sea to carry electrical power from one place to another place. Job Location Sumatra Java Interconnection development work crosses 4 (four) provinces, namely: 1. South Sumatra 2. Lampung 3. Banten 4. West Java. The Sumatra Sumatra Interconnection Development Unit PT PLN has competent human resources from various educational backgrounds who carry out the day-to-day operational activities of the organization. Besides that, the employee performance of the Sumatra Java Interconnection Development Unit PT PLN has a tendency to experience a decline in performance.

According to Bangun (2015), performance (performance) is the result of work achieved by a person based on job requirements (job requirements). One of the factors that influence the increase in HR performance through internal factors (individual) employees, namely ability (ability). One's abilities are determined by the intelligence he possesses, namely intellectual intelligence. According to Widodo (2012) in Sulastris, et al (2016) intellectual intelligence is intellectual ability, analysis, logic, and ratio. This intelligence is the intelligence to receive, store, and process information into facts. intellectual intelligence is the ability to solve problems or create a product that is valuable in one or several cultural backgrounds. The following is a pre survey survey of intellectual intelligence.

What is the Intelligence Level Can Increase Employee Performance PT. PLN ?

The world of work is closely related to intellectual intelligence possessed by someone. A worker who has a high IQ is expected to produce better performance than those who have a low IQ. This is because those who have high IQs are easier to absorb the knowledge given so that their ability to solve problems related to their work will be better.

In addition to intellectual intelligence, another factor that influences employee performance is emotional intelligence. According to Goleman (2015: 13) emotional intelligence is the ability of self-control, enthusiasm and perseverance and the ability to motivate yourself. Emotional intelligence rests on feelings of character and moral instincts. There is increasing evidence that basic ethical attitudes in life originate from the underlying emotional abilities. People who are controlled by impulses who lack self-control will suffer from lack of moral control. A person who with good emotional intelligence is most likely to succeed in his life because he is able to master the thinking habits that encourage productivity.

The world of work has a variety of problems that must be faced by employees, such as intense competition, demanding tasks, uncomfortable work atmosphere and relationship problems with others. These problems in the world of work are not those that require intellectual abilities but in solving these problems more emotional abilities or emotional intelligence are needed. In addition to intellectual and emotional intelligence, other factors that influence employee performance are spiritual intelligence. According to Khavari (2006) in Dharmawan (2013: 849) spiritual intelligence is intelligence on the human soul. Spiritual intelligence is the hidden potential possessed by everyone.

Spiritual intelligence gives us the eye to see positive values in every problem and wisdom to deal with problems and reap the benefits of them. Spiritual intelligence (SQ) is the ability to respond to and treat others like oneself and the motivation underlying each action is done not solely for self-interest but more attention to the interests of the people on the basis of equality as fellow creatures of God.

Today the world of work brings more concentration on spiritual issues. The workers get the values of life not only at home, but they also look for every meaning of life that comes from their work environment. Those who can give meaning to their lives and bring spirituality into their work environment will make them better people so that the resulting performance is also better than those who work without spiritual intelligence. Based on the background of the problem, it appears how important intellectual intelligence, emotional intelligence and spiritual intelligence in improving employee performance. So the objectives of the study are (1) to analyze the influence of intellectual intelligence on employee performance, (2) to analyze the influence of emotional intelligence on employee performance, and (3) to analyze the influence of spiritual intelligence on employee performance.

The research contributions that are expected to appear in this study are (1) theoretical contributions, the results of this study are expected to be a reference in similar research related to work discipline, compensation, and training on employee performance. (2) practical contributions, the results of this study can be used as a reference, for consideration in taking a policy in improving the quality of human resources in organizations or companies.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Performance is a translation of performance which means the work of a worker, a management process or an organization as a whole, where the results of the work must be demonstrated concretely and can be measured (compared to predetermined standards) (Suprpto, 2018). It can be concluded that employee performance is a result of work that has been achieved by employees or employees in accordance with the criteria and standards that have previously been set at a certain period. According to Bangun (2012), performance (performance) is the result of work achieved by a person based on job requirements (job requirements). Whereas according to Robbins and Coulter (2010) performance is the work of individuals or groups in achieving the goals set by the organization in accordance with a predetermined time period.

According to J.P. Chaplin in Rahman (2011), intelligence is defined as the ability to adapt and meet the demands of the situation (environment) faced quickly and effectively, use abstract concepts effectively, and understand relationships and learn them quickly. Whereas intellectual intelligence is as a totality of one's ability to act with certain goals, think rationally, and deal with the environment effectively.

Emotional intelligence is a subset of social intelligence that involves the ability to monitor social feelings that involve abilities in others, sorting through everything and using this information to influence the formation of emotional intelligence.

According to Wijayanti (2012), emotional intelligence is a capability in managing our responses and emotions when dealing with other people, situations, interaction problems, and stressful conditions, so as to get effective results. Or our understanding of others so that we can manage all situations and can interact with win-win ways. While Goleman (2015) emotional intelligence is the ability of self-control, enthusiasm and perseverance and the ability to motivate yourself. Emotional intelligence rests on feelings of character and moral instincts.

What is the Intelligence Level Can Increase Employee Performance PT. PLN ?

Spiritual intelligence is intelligence to deal with and solve problems of meaning and value, namely placing behavior and human life in the context of broader and richer meanings, and assessing that a person's actions or way of life are more meaningful than others. According to Dharmawan (2013), spiritual intelligence is intelligence on the human soul. Spiritual intelligence is the hidden potential possessed by everyone. Spiritual intelligence gives us the eye to see positive values in every problem and wisdom to deal with problems and reap the benefits of them.

III. RESEARCH METHODS

Research design is the main design of research that states the methods and procedures used by researchers in the selection, collection and analysis of data. Research design provides a procedure for obtaining information needed to compile or resolve problems in research. The design in this study is quantitative associative. Quantitative research can be interpreted as a research method based on a sample philosophy of positivism used to examine a population or a particular sample, data collection using research instruments, data analysis is quantitative / statistical, with the aim to test the hypothesis that has been set. According to Sugiyono (2016), associative research is a research that is asking about the relationship between two or more variables.

1. Operational Definition of Variables

Variables are everything in the form of what is determined by the researcher to be studied, so that information about it is obtained and conclusions are drawn. In other words, it can be interpreted as an attribute or the nature or value of a person, object, or activity that has certain variations set by the researcher, to be studied and drawn conclusions. In this study the variables used are:

- a. Intellectual intelligence. According to Ratnasari (2015), intellectual intelligence is the totality of the ability of a person to act with certain goals, think rationally, and deal with the environment effectively.
- b. Emotional Intelligence. According to Goleman (2015: 13), emotional intelligence is the ability to control oneself, enthusiasm and perseverance and the ability to motivate oneself. Emotional intelligence rests on feelings of character and moral instincts. There is increasing evidence that basic ethical attitudes in life originate from the underlying emotional abilities
- c. Spiritual Intelligence. According to Zohar and Marshall (2005) in Notoprasetyo (2012: 77), spiritual intelligence is an intelligence to deal with and solve problems of meaning and value, namely placing behavior and human life in the context of broader and richer meanings, and judging that actions or ways of life someone is more meaningful than others.
- d. Employee performance. Performance (performance) is the result of work achieved by a person based on job requirements (job requirements).

2. Research Variables

The various variables in the study according to Sugiyono (2016: 39) can be explained as follows:

- a. Free variable. The independent variable is a variable that influences or causes the change or the emergence of the dependent variable. namely variables that affect the dependent variable. The independent variables in this study consisted of (1) Intellectual Intelligence (X1), (2) Emotional Intelligence (X2), and (3) Spiritual Intelligence (X3).
- b. Dependent variable. Dependent variable is a variable that is influenced or that becomes a result, because of the existence of independent variables. Dependent variable which is influenced by independent variables. The dependent variable in this study is Employee Performance (Y).

3. Research Population

Population is a generalization area consisting of objects / subjects that have certain qualities and characteristics determined by researchers to be studied and then conclusions drawn. The population in this study were 63 employees of PT PLN (Persero) Main Unit of the Sumatra-Java Interconnection Development.

4. Research Samples

The sample is a portion of that population. If the population is large, and researchers are not likely to learn all that exists in the population, for example due to limited funds, energy and time, the researcher can use samples taken from that population. The sampling technique used in this study is a non-probability sampling, namely saturated sampling. Saturated sampling is a sampling technique if all members of the population are used as samples. (Sugiyono, 2016: 85). The number of samples in the study were 63 employees at PT PLN (Persero) the Main Unit of the Sumatra-Java Interconnection Development.

5. Data Collection Techniques

Data collection techniques, in this study include the following:

- a. Observation. Observation is a complex process, a process composed of various biological and psychological processes. Two of the most important are the processes of observation and memory. In this study observational researchers at PT. PLN (Persero) Main Unit of Sumatra-Java Interconnection Development, having its address at Jalan Aipda KS. Tubun I / II Petamburan, West Jakarta.
- b. Questionnaire / Questionnaire. Questionnaires are data collection techniques that are carried out by giving a set of questions or written statements to the respondent to answer. The statements or questions in the questionnaire will be measured using a Likert scale type

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1). Multiple Linear Regression Test

Multiple linear regression analysis is an analysis to determine the effect or relationship linearly between independent variables (intellectual intelligence, emotional intelligence, spiritual intelligence) on the dependent variable, namely employee performance. Used to predict or predict the direction of the relationship of a dependent variable based on independent variables. In this study, the regression equations obtained are:

$$EP = 0.415 + 0.819 II + 0.297 EI + 0.433 SI$$

Where:

EP = Employee Performance

II = Intellectual Intelligence

EI = Emotional Intelligence

SI = Spiritual Intelligence

The regression equation above has the meaning:

- a. The constant value (a) is 0.415 which can be interpreted if intellectual intelligence, emotional intelligence, spiritual intelligence value is 0, then employee performance is worth 0.415
- b. The multiple regression coefficient value of intellectual intelligence variable (b1) is positive which is equal to 0.819. It can be interpreted that every increase in intellectual intelligence is 1 unit, it will improve employee performance by 0.819 units assuming other independent variables remain.
- c. The value of multiple regression coefficients of emotional intelligence (b2) is positive that is equal to 0.297. It can be interpreted that every increase in emotional intelligence by 1 unit, it will improve employee performance by 0.297 units assuming other independent variables remain.
- d. The value of multiple regression coefficients of spiritual intelligence (b3) is positive that is equal to 0.433. It can be interpreted that every increase in spiritual intelligence is 1 unit, it will improve employee performance by 0.433 units assuming other independent variables remain.

2). Determination Coefficient Test (R²)

The coefficient of determination shows how much the ability of independent variables (intellectual intelligence, emotional intelligence, spiritual intelligence) in explaining the variance of the dependent variable, namely employee performance. The test results of the coefficient of determination, in this study are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Output of the Coefficient of Determination (R²)

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	,740 ^a	,547	,524	4,681

Table 1 shows that Adjusted R Square is 0.524, this means that the variables of intellectual intelligence, emotional intelligence and spiritual intelligence have an effect of 52.4% on employee performance. And the remainder of (100% - 52.4% = 47.6%) is influenced by other factors not explained in this study.

What is the Intelligence Level Can Increase Employee Performance PT. PLN ?

3). Simultaneous Significance Test (Test Statistic F)

Simultaneous significance test (ANOVA test or F test), is used to test together, the effect of several independent variables on the dependent variable. The results of the simultaneous significance test (ANOVA test or F test), in this study are presented in Table 2.

Tabel 2. Uji Anova

	Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	1560,737	3	520,246	23,739	,000 ^b
	Residual	1292,977	59	21,915		
	Total	2853,714	62			

Table 2 shows that the value of F count > F table ($23,739 > 4,149$), then H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted. And the probability value (significance) is $0,000 < 0,05$ so there is a significant effect. It can be concluded that intellectual intelligence, emotional intelligence, and spiritual intelligence together have a significant effect on employee performance.

4). Test the Significance of Individual Parameters (Test Statistics t)

Test the significance of individual parameters (statistical test t), used to determine the effect of independent variables on the dependent variable. Test results of significance of individual parameters (statistical test t), in this study are presented in Table 3.

Tabel 3. Uji Statistik t

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			
1	(Constant)	,415	5,183		,080	,937
	II	,819	,137	,562	5,984	,000
	EI	,297	,121	,227	2,452	,017
	SI	,433	,163	,236	2,661	,010

Table 3 shows that the significance values of KI, KE, and KS are less than 0.05, it can be concluded that (1) Intellectual intelligence (II) has a significance value of $0,000 < 0,05$, which means that intellectual intelligence has a significant effect on employee performance. (2) Emotional intelligence (EI) has a significant value of $0,017 < 0,05$, meaning that emotional intelligence has a significant effect on employee performance. (3) Spiritual intelligence (SI) has a significance value of $0,010 < 0,05$, meaning that spiritual intelligence has a significant effect on employee performance.

V. CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

1). Conclusion

From the results of the analysis of the research conducted, conclusions can be drawn as follows:

1. Intellectual intelligence has a positive and significant effect on the employee performance of the Sumatra - Java Interconnection Development Unit of PT PLN (Persero). This shows, if the intellectual intelligence of employees increases, it will improve employee performance.
2. Emotional intelligence has a positive and significant effect on the employee performance of the Sumatra - Java Interconnection Development Unit of PT PLN (Persero). This shows, if the emotional intelligence of employees increases, it will improve employee performance.
3. Spiritual intelligence has a positive and significant effect on the employee performance of the Sumatra - Java Interconnection Development Unit of PT PLN (Persero). This shows, if the employee's spiritual intelligence increases, it will improve employee performance.

What is the Intelligence Level Can Increase Employee Performance PT. PLN ?

2). Suggestion

From the results of the analysis of the research conducted, the following suggestions can be made:

1. Companies are advised to hold discussions between employees and management on a regular basis to refresh the details of employee jobs so that all problems can be well communicated.
2. Companies are advised to be able to disburse the work environment and form a better work environment by increasing activities outside of work to refresh employees such as recitation, outbound, fangath, joint sports etc.
3. Companies are advised to more facilitate the development of employees outside the office eg educational assistance in the form of cooperation with educational institutions related to employee development.

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What is the Intelligence Level Can Increase Employee Performance PT. PLN ?

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